

Research papers

Performance analysis of the Høje Taastrup water pit thermal energy storage

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ABSTRACT

Pit thermal energy storage (PTES) is a large-scale low-cost storage technology for district heating that has almost exclusively been used in combination with solar thermal collectors for seasonal heat storage. However, PTES systems can also benefit non-solar based district heating systems, which was demonstrated in 2023 with the construction of the first large-scale short-term PTES in Høje Taastrup, Denmark. This storage represents the current state-of-the-art, particularly due to innovations in the lid and diffuser design, the development of a new high-temperature liner material, and the presence of a research-grade monitoring system. This study aimed to present the design improvements of the PTES in Høje Taastrup, analyze the impact of short-term operation, and conduct a performance analysis in terms of storage efficiency and stratification. It was successfully demonstrated that PTES can be used for short-term operation, provided they use liner materials that can withstand exposure to temperatures up to at least 90 °C for long periods. Additionally, the single-plate diffuser solution placed at the edge of the storage did not seem to negatively affect stratification. Overall, the short-term operated PTES in Høje Taastrup featured 89% energy and 75% exergy efficiency, thus performing similarly to the seasonal PTES in Dronninglund.

1. Introduction

District heating systems supply heat from central plants by circulating hot water in insulated pipes. One of the key benefits of district heating is its ability to integrate combined heat and power (CHP) plants, which simultaneously generate electricity and utilize the excess heat that would otherwise go to waste. This process significantly improves energy efficiency making district heating a cost-effective solution. Additionally, district heating systems are highly versatile, as they can utilize various heat sources, making them an adaptable and sustainable solution for modern energy needs.

In Denmark, 66% of the heat demand is covered using district heating (DH) [1]. The DH network in Copenhagen, Denmark, illustrated in Fig. 1, is one of the largest heating networks in the world, annually supplying approximately 30,000 TJ of heat. The network is operated by four main companies, namely VEKS, CTR, HOFOR, and Vestforbrænding. The different heat supply areas are connected by a transmission grid, which is a 160 km pipe system operating at 25 bar and 110 °C (illustrated by the thick black curves in Fig. 1) [2]. Additionally, the greater Copenhagen DH system has 20 distribution companies that are municipality or consumer-owned.

The Copenhagen DH grid is supplied by numerous different generation units based on different technologies, including combined heat and power (CHP) plants, more than 50 peak boiler units, as well as electric

and biomass boilers, heat pumps, and industrial surplus heat [4]. Dispatching of the different generation units is determined based on bids made to a centralized heat market (hour-to-hour and day-to-day). This way, technologies with low production costs are prioritized, minimizing the overall heat production costs while constantly meeting the heat demand.

The CHP plants in the Copenhagen network are based on biomass or waste incineration and contribute the largest share of the heat generation. As CHP plants participate in both the heating and electricity markets, the optimal operation depends on the demand and price in both markets. From the perspective of the electricity market, it is favorable to operate at full capacity when electricity prices are high, which may not match the demand for district heating. Having thermal energy storage (TES) adds flexibility, which is crucial for optimizing the operation of the entire energy system, both from an economic and environmental perspective. TES systems are also useful for managing external heat sources that DH companies cannot control, such as excess heat from industrial processes [2]. Depending on the storage duration, TES systems can be roughly classified into short- and long-term (or seasonal).

A diverse portfolio of generation technologies, as well as storage solutions, is considered essential for robust DH systems [5]. However, since the Copenhagen network is mainly based on CHP generation,

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Fig. 1. The district heating grid of Copenhagen.
Source: Adapted from [3].

short-term TES solutions have been considered more advantageous as they allow for optimizing CHP plant production, providing peak hour load, thereby reducing the need for fossil-fueled peak boilers and balancing daily heat load variations. Prior to 2023, the main energy storage capacity in the Copenhagen district heating system comprised two 20,000 m³ water tank thermal energy storage (TTES) systems [2].

In 2017, a feasibility study was conducted to investigate the potential gains of increased flexibility by increasing the storage capacity in the Copenhagen DH system [6]. Simulations of the DH systems with different levels of energy storage were conducted using the Balmorel software [7]. The simulations were based on hourly data and assumptions of how the Copenhagen DH network is expected to develop during the lifetime of the storage. The simulations for the year 2025 showed that adding a 70,000 m³ water heat storage could lower the heat generation from expensive peak gas boilers (reduction of 24 GWh/y) and increase heat and electricity generation from waste and biomass CHP plants (25 GWh/y increase in heat). Additionally, it was expected that heat generation from heat pumps would increase (1 GWh/year extra heat production). Overall, a reduction in CO₂ emission of 10,000–15,000 tons/y, and a reduction of system costs of 5–7 million DKK/year was expected.

Based on the feasibility study, it was decided to construct a 70,000 m³ pit thermal energy storage (PTES) in Høje Taastrup, which was completed in 2023. A PTES was chosen over a traditional TTES due to the very low construction costs of PTES for large-scale systems, which is due to the simple construction of PTES. The PTES was built with the aim to be operated as a weekly heat storage, whose operation would be based on a 7-day forecast. The forecast would be based on heat demand, production capacity, electricity price, and fuel price.

A PTES is a large water reservoir dug into the ground, lined with a watertight polymer liner (to prevent water from leaking to the ground), and covered with a floating insulating lid to reduce heat losses [8]. PTES is a relatively new technology, with the first large-scale (>50,000 m³) water-based commercial system being constructed in Marstal, Denmark, in 2012. In general, most large-scale PTES systems are located in Denmark and have so far been used only for seasonal heat storage. Table 1 shows an overview of the existing PTES systems in Denmark. The low efficiencies of some of the systems mainly stem from the poor durability and performance of older lid constructions [8].

It should be noted that the performance of most PTES is usually documented only for the first 1–3 years of operation. Thus, there is

Table 1

Existing large-scale PTES in Denmark.

PTES	Start year	Volume [m ³]	Efficiency [%]	Ref.
Marstal	2012	75,000	66	[9,10]
Dronninglund	2014	60,000	90	[11,12]
Gram	2015	122,000	60	[13,14]
Vojens	2015	200,000	–	[15]
Toftlund	2017	70,000	70	[16,17]

no long-term monitoring and evaluation of the performance of the existing PTES systems, and for some commercial systems, there is no information regarding their operation (e.g., the PTES in Vojens, Denmark).

As previously mentioned, most PTES systems are operated as seasonal heat storage. Before the construction of the PTES in Høje Taastrup, the only PTES used for short-term heat storage was in Tibet; however, this storage was only 15,000 m³, and data from its operation are not available. Additionally, the PTES in Høje Taastrup has some distinctively different features from existing systems. For example, the shape of the PTES is very oblong (narrow rectangle with long sides), and the inlet/outlet diffusers were installed near the side wall of the storage and not in the center. Before the investigations conducted in the present work, it was unclear whether this would negatively impact the storage efficiency and stratification.

During the storage design stage, it was expected that the top water layer would be constantly around 90 °C. Consequently, different liner solutions that could withstand such high temperatures were investigated. Similarly, the PTES lid construction had not before been constantly exposed to 90 °C water temperature, posing questions regarding the performance and durability of the components. Overall, the PTES in Høje Taastrup represents the current state-of-the-art PTES system, in terms of the lid construction, liner solution, and diffuser design, in addition to the monitoring system. All these make the PTES in Høje Taastrup a unique case study, especially since its operation data has been made freely available as part of the FLEX-TES research project [18]. The monitoring data from the PTES in Høje Taastrup used for this analysis are publicly available as described in [19].

This article aims to investigate the most recent developments of the PTES technology and their impact on performance using the Høje Taastrup PTES as a case study, also offering a thorough explanation of

Fig. 2. The PTES connection to the main transmission and local distribution grid. Note that the PTES is charged from the main transmission grid but can only be discharged to the local distribution grid. More details on this are given in Section 4.1.

its design and operation. The study includes an analysis of the Høje Taastrup PTES monitoring data from the start of its operation in 2023, investigating the following key questions:

- Can large-scale PTES systems be used successfully for short-term heat storage?
- How does the performance of the PTES in Høje Taastrup compare to existing PTES systems?
- To what degree is stratification affected by the diffusers being installed at one end of the storage?

2. The PTES in Høje Taastrup

The PTES in Høje Taastrup was constructed as part of the FLEX-TES research project [18] and started its operation in February 2023. The purpose of the FLEX-TES research project was to demonstrate the use of PTES systems for short-term storage. As shown in Fig. 1, the storage is located west of Copenhagen (latitude: 55.666°N, longitude: 12.252°E). The storage connection to the DH transmission and distribution grid can be seen in Fig. 2. A plot of land outside the city zoning was desired due to the much lower cost. However, finding a sufficiently large plot of land near Copenhagen, close to existing district heating infrastructure, and outside the city zoning was challenging. Notably, the selected plot of land had some restrictions, i.e., a highway to the south and a water pipe to the north, which dictated the shape and size of the PTES.

To investigate the research questions, an extensive monitoring program was developed, which included measurements of charged/discharged energy, flow rates, storage water temperature, ground temperature, lid temperature and humidity, etc. Specific information on the installed sensors is provided in [19].

2.1. Overview of the storage construction

The soil excavation for the PTES construction started in the spring of 2020 (see Fig. 3). A leakage detection system was installed after the excavation, consisting of more than 1000 sensors arranged in a 2 by 2-meter grid pattern along the side and bottom of the PTES. In the event of water leaking from the storage, the electrical current between sensors in the affected area would increase, enabling precise localization of the leak.

Afterward, a geotextile, geonet, and polypropylene (PP) liner were installed along the sides and bottom of the storage (see Fig. 3). Next, a protective polyethylene (PE) liner was installed on top of the PP liner (black liner in Fig. 4). The protective liner was used to limit the PP liner's UV exposure and soiling of the water during construction and was discarded when the lid was installed.

Filling of the storage with water started in November 2020. Treated water from the VEKS transmission pipes was used to minimize corrosion of the steel components (e.g., diffusers). For more information on the water quality, the reader is referred to [20].

At the end of January 2021, an alarm was raised by the leakage detection system. Investigations showed the liner had multiple cracks along one of the side walls. The crack formation was attributed to wooden pegs that had been used to pierce through the liner in order to keep it in place on the embankment, combined with sub-zero temperatures that made the liner brittle. The damage was so extensive that the entire liner was replaced. Thus, the storage was emptied, and a new liner was installed that included a plasticizer additive, enabling the liner to maintain some plasticity down to $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. After installing the new liner and the protective PE cover, the water-filling was re-initiated on October 25, 2021.

Water filling was completed in mid-March 2022, after which the lid construction and installation of the monitoring equipment began. At the end of October 2022, heating of the water and testing of control functions was initiated. Finally, the PTES was fully charged by January 2023 and began commercial operation on February 15, 2023.

2.2. Liner and lid

For PTES systems operated as seasonal storages, the temperature at the top of the storage reaches $90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ during the charging period (usually March to August) and is then lowered as the storage is discharged. The storage temperature when it is completely discharged is typically at the return temperature of the district heating network but may reach as low as $8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ if the PTES is used as a source for a heat pump. However, since the PTES in Høje Taastrup was operated as a short-term heat storage (weekly storage duration), the lid and the top liner would be almost constantly exposed to $90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This presents a challenge for the performance and lifetime of the high-density polyethylene (HDPE) liner material that had been used for seasonal PTES. As an alternative, the Austrian gigaTES research project [21] investigated the use of high-temperature resistant polypropylene (PP-HTR) liners, which would ensure a long lifetime at high temperatures (i.e., more than 30 years at $95\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). The downside of using a PP liner was that the material had only been tested in the lab and never used in an actual system. Another alternative was using a double-layered HDPE liner; however, this was deemed too costly and was also an untested solution. The HDPE solution had an estimated lifetime of 20 years at $90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, regardless if a single or double layer was used. Eventually, it was decided to proceed with the single PP liner, which was used for the sides and bottom of the PTES, as well as a floating liner, separating the water surface from the lid.

The modular lid concept developed by Aalborg CSP was selected to be used for the PTES, a solution that had already been tested in Marstal and showed promising results. The installed lid featured different insulation layers (with different temperature resistance), as shown in Fig. 5. The two insulation layers closest to the water were NOMATEC XLPa 30HTL, a cross-linked polyolefin foam produced by the company NMC [22], featuring high-temperature resistance. The top two insulation layers were standard expanded polystyrene (XPS) insulation. The lid was divided into eight modules to handle rainwater effectively. Each module had a slope toward its center where a pump was placed to remove rainwater. The slope of each module was created using varying levels of pebbles (see Fig. 4 (right)).

2.3. Diffusers

The PTES was designed to be charged and discharged using three insulated pipes, each having a diffuser to reduce mixing in the storage and establish a high degree of stratification. The diffusers were placed near the side wall closest to the pump station, which reduced the length of the pipes (and cost). This also avoided deeper excavations which is necessary when installing the pipes under the PTES. For more information on the storage dimensions, the reader is referred to [19].

The feasibility study identified the desired charge/discharge rate of the PTES to be 30 MW, which, assuming a supply temperature of $90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Fig. 3. Excavation (left) and liner installation (right).

Fig. 4. Diffuser installation (left) and completed lid (right).

Fig. 5. Cross-sectional view of the lid construction from the company Aalborg CSP. Source: Adapted from [23].

and a return of 45 °C, corresponds to a flow rate of approximately 600 m³/h. The diffusers were designed to ensure that the incoming water velocity to the storage would be laminar flow at 0.03 m/s in order to achieve minimal mixing. The top and bottom diffusers had a diameter of 5 m and consisted of a single plate, where the lid and bottom surfaces acted as the upper and lower plates for the upper and lower diffuser, respectively. The middle diffuser consisted of two parallel plates with a diameter of 3 m and a vertical spacing of 0.4 m (see Fig. 4 for an overview of the diffusers). This storage was the first to use single-plate diffusers, which are beneficial due to less material usage, but more importantly, avoid any inaccessible water volume above the top diffuser or below the bottom diffuser.

The top diffuser plate was placed at a height of 13.8 m and the bottom diffuser plate was at 0.45 m. The bottom plate of the middle diffuser was placed at a height of 10.5 m, such that approximately half of the storage volume was above it and half below it.

It should be noted that the presence of a middle diffuser is not essential for storage operation. Assuming that the heat source can always

deliver the desired temperature (e.g., the Copenhagen DH transmission grid is operated up to 110 °C), the storage can be operated only using the top and bottom diffusers. The middle diffuser was installed to allow for some additional flexibility in the storage operation, e.g., enabling water discharge at a lower temperature by mixing it with hotter water from the top diffuser. Generally, a middle diffuser is very useful for seasonal PTES since they are charged with heat from solar thermal collectors that may not always be able to deliver heat at the required temperature.

2.4. Construction cost

The costs of the individual PTES components are shown in Table 2, summing to a total project cost of approximately 12 million €. The positive economic gains of the storage operation were estimated during the feasibility study to be 1.05 million €/y, with operation costs at 0.16 million €/y. This corresponds to an estimated simple payback period of 12 years and an internal rate of return (IRR) of 7.5%, assuming a lifetime of 20 years (although the lifetime is expected to be longer than 20 years) [20]. It should be noted that these calculations do not include the land cost, as information was not available regarding this.

The expected economic benefits are due to (1) optimization of heat production in relation to the electricity market (higher income from electricity sales), (2) reduced operation of expensive gas boilers during peak demand periods, and (3) increased production from cheap waste incineration plants in the summer. It should be noted that the expenses related to the construction and operation of the storage were shared among all of the major heat producers in the Copenhagen district heating network according to their expected long-term economic benefits.

It should be noted that the PTES cost is significantly higher compared to existing PTES systems [23], mainly due to rises in material prices.

Table 2
Project costs [20]. All costs are in 2018 values.

Component	Cost [10 ⁶ €]
Soil excavation and shaping	0.55
Design and supervision	1.14
Storage and pump station	6.05
Heat exchanger building	2.42
District heating pipes	0.94
Electrical installations	0.44
Water filling	0.51
Total	12.05

3. Methods

As mentioned in the introduction, the PTES in Høje Taastrup features distinctively different characteristics from existing systems in terms of its shape, lid construction, operating strategy, liner material, and diffuser design. For this reason, there is a large interest within the scientific community regarding its operation and performance. Additionally, several new PTES are in the planning stage in Europe, and many of these projects are looking to learn from the experiences of the Høje Taastrup PTES. In order to evaluate the performance of the storage, investigations of the storage efficiency and stratification were conducted. While several definitions and formulas exist for evaluating these parameters, it was decided to follow the methods described in [24].

3.1. Efficiency

The storage efficiency was assessed in terms of energy and exergy. For calculating the energy efficiency, the following expression was used, as suggested by Sifnaios et al. [24]:

$$\eta_E = \frac{E_{out}}{E_{in} - \Delta E_{int}} \quad (1)$$

where E_{out} is the energy discharged from the system and E_{in} is the charged energy. ΔE_{int} is the change in the internal energy of the storage system, i.e., the difference between the internal energy at the end and start of the period under consideration.

Following the same convention, for calculating exergy efficiency, the formula suggested by Rosen et al. [25] was modified to include the internal exergy change:

$$\eta_X = \frac{Ex_{out}}{Ex_{in} - \Delta Ex_{int}} \quad (2)$$

where Ex_{in} is the exergy added by charging the storage, and Ex_{out} is the exergy removed when discharging the storage. ΔEx_{int} is the change in the internal energy of the storage system, i.e., the difference between the internal energy at the end and start of the period under consideration. It should be noted that a key difference between energy and exergy efficiency is that exergy efficiency also accounts for the level of stratification, as mixing reduces exergy. The minimum stored temperature in the PTES was used as a reference state. The reference state was constant for all exergy calculations.

3.2. Thermal stratification

Thermal stratification was investigated using the stratification coefficient, St , by Wu and Bannerot [26] and the normalized exergy destruction by Sifnaios et al. [24]. For calculating the stratification indicators, the water domain of the PTES was divided into 26 discrete layers corresponding to the position of the installed temperature sensors. Each layer was assumed to have a uniform temperature, measured by one temperature sensor. For more information on the sensor position, the reader is referred to [19].

The stratification coefficient expresses the degree of thermal stratification based on the deviation of the storage temperature profile relative to the mean temperature. It can be calculated using the following equation:

$$St = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{m_i \cdot (T_i - T_{avg})^2}{m_{total}} \quad (3)$$

where N is the total number of layers, T_i is the temperature and m_i is the mass of the i th layer, T_{avg} is the average storage temperature, and m_{total} is the total mass of the storage system.

Exergy destruction is the sum of the exergy destroyed due to mixing, thermal conduction, and diffusion, and can be calculated from the exergy balance of the PTES:

$$\Delta Ex_{destr, norm} = \frac{\Delta Ex_{flow} - \Delta Ex_{store} - \Delta Ex_{loss}}{V_{total}} \quad (4)$$

where ΔEx_{flow} is the net exergy added/removed from the storage through charging/discharging, ΔEx_{store} is the change in exergy stored in the PTES during the time period investigated, ΔEx_{loss} is the exergy lost due to heat loss, and V_{total} is the total volume of the PTES. The reason why the normalized exergy destruction was chosen was to be able to compare the obtained values to PTES of different sizes (e.g., see [24]).

4. Results

The storage started commercial operation in mid-February 2023. However, the first year of operation was mainly used to implement and test a forecasting-based control strategy; thus, the storage operation was somewhat limited in 2023. Additionally, not all sensors were installed from the beginning of operation, meaning some data were missing during the first year. Since January 2024, charging and discharging of the PTES have been scheduled by Varmelast, which is the independent load dispatching center for the Copenhagen district heating grid. At the start, only a forecasting horizon of 24 h was used; however, toward the end of 2024, the forecasting horizon was extended to 7 days, which was the original plan.

4.1. Storage operation and energy content

The storage water temperature profile for 2024 is presented in Fig. 6 (top). It can be observed that the operation temperature was between approximately 48–90 °C. The charging periods can be identified when the water temperature increases (lighter color), for example, in mid-February. In contrast, discharging periods can be identified when the water temperature decreases (darker color), for example, in mid-June. The charge and discharge periods can be directly correlated with the change in storage energy content and weekly charge/discharge amounts shown in Fig. 6 (bottom). In order to evaluate the PTES energy content, it should be noted that the maximum storage capacity is estimated to be 3300 MWh. This value was calculated using the minimum design temperature of 48.5 °C.

The maximum observed charge and discharge rates were 30 and 23 MW, respectively, which is in line with the design values of 30 MW. The storage was mainly operated in the winter and spring of 2024, while little activity occurred in the summer and autumn. The main reason for this was due to the PTES being unable to discharge heat back to the transmission grid. This was because the maximum storage temperature in the PTES was 90 °C, while the main transmission grid was operated at 110 °C. Thus, the storage could only discharge heat to the local distribution grid of Høje Taastrup, which operated at a lower temperature. Additionally, some temporary capacity limitations in the Høje Taastrup distribution grid and challenges with interconnecting local distribution grids during the summer combined with a relatively low heating load during the summer and autumn of 2024 resulted in reductions in the storage discharge compared to the optimal operation.

Fig. 6. (top) Storage water temperatures and (bottom) weekly charged/discharged energy and energy content.

It should be noted that the storage was designed with an aim to discharge a maximum capacity of 30 MW during the winter period (approx. 6 months) and less than 30 MW in the summer months, where the heat demand in the distribution grid sets the limit of the discharge capacity.

Work is ongoing to expand the distribution grid in Høje Taastrup, which will result in higher heat demand and, thus, less restriction on storage discharge during summer. The mean charging rate for 2024 was 15 MW, while for discharge, it was only 8 MW. These values are expected to increase with the expansion of the distribution grid and improvements in the control strategy.

Fig. 6 (bottom) shows that the storage was charging and discharging every week of the year. There is also not an overall seasonal trend in the stored energy, which is unique in that it demonstrates the first instances of a large-scale PTES being used for short-term energy storage.

4.2. Temperature profile

Based on the feasibility study, the storage top water layer was expected to be at 90 °C constantly. However, it can be seen from Fig. 6 (top) that the water temperature immediately under the lid is not always that high. Specifically, it was found that the top water layer temperature was higher than 80 °C 80% of the operation time and higher than 85 °C 60% of the time. Although the top water temperature was not constantly at 90 °C, it is still much higher compared to the existing seasonally operated PTES. For example, in Dronninglund, the top water layer temperature was higher than 80 °C only 35% of the time and higher than 85 °C only 8% of the time. This difference highlights the importance of selecting high temperature-resistant liners for short-term operated PTES.

The polypropylene (PP) liner supplier stated that the lifetime of the liner was > 30 years when exposed to a temperature of 95 °C based

Table 3

Mean temperature and flow rate for each diffuser during charging and discharging operations for 2024.

Mode	Diffuser	Mean temperature [°C]	Mean flow rate [m ³ /hr]
Charge	Top	89	330
	Bottom	50	330
Discharge	Top	83	133
	Middle	77	76
	Top+Middle	81	209
	Bottom	50	209

on laboratory tests. However, since this liner solution had never been tested in a PTES before, it was decided by the operator not to expose it to temperatures higher than 90 °C as a safety precaution. Thus, as seen in Table 3, the mean temperature of the top diffuser during charging was 89 °C.

Table 3 presents the mean temperatures and flow rates of the individual diffusers during charging and discharging. It can be observed that the middle diffuser was only used during discharge to enable the discharge of water at a lower temperature by mixing it with hotter water from the top diffuser.

4.3. Stratification

The PTES in Høje Taastrup was the first PTES to have the diffusers placed near the side wall of the storage, which could potentially affect the stratification — particularly given the oblong shape of the storage, resulting in a large distance from the diffusers to the far end of the storage. Given the lack of experience with such a design, it was of interest to assess whether the storage would achieve a uniform horizontal

Fig. 7. Temperature difference between the east and west sides of the PTES.

temperature. Fig. 7 shows the temperature difference between the temperature sensors at the east and west ends of the PTES at four different depths. In general, it can be observed that the temperature difference between the east and west sides was less than 1 K. Considering the accuracy of the sensors (± 0.35 K) and the uncertainty of the sensor depth, the conclusion is that there is not a noticeable difference in the horizontal temperature distribution in the storage.

However, horizontal stratification does not necessarily ensure that the storage performs well. Vertical stratification is required in the storage, maintaining the warm water at the top and the colder water at the bottom. A high degree of vertical stratification indicates little mixing between the layers, increasing the amount of energy that can be discharged. Fig. 8 shows selected vertical temperature profiles in the PTES during charging and discharging. It can be observed that, in general, higher water temperatures are stored at the top of the storage (under the lid area). However, there is a small water layer right under the lid where there is a temperature inversion, driven by the heat losses through the lid. The curves indicate a high temperature gradient at different storage depths, suggesting a high degree of stratification. In particular, the temperature gradient is much steeper for the discharge scenario than for the charge scenario. This is in part due to the tapered shape of the storage, i.e., 1 m of thermocline at the top becomes much thicker as it is shifted downwards during charging. Additionally, lower flow rates were used during the storage discharge (see Table 3) which tends to have a positive effect on stratification. However, evaluating stratification simply by relying on these plots is not sufficient.

For this reason, and to compare the stratification in the PTES in Høje Taastrup with other systems, the Stratification coefficient and the normalized exergy destruction were calculated. For the Stratification coefficient, a higher value indicates a higher degree of stratification, whereas the coefficient approaches zero when the storage has a uniform temperature. For the PTES in Høje Taastrup, the maximum value of the Stratification coefficient for 2024 was 330 K^2 , whereas the mean value was 152 K^2 . For comparison, the maximum values for Marstal and Dronninglund were 169 K^2 and 538 K^2 , respectively. Regarding the mean values, Marstal had 64 K^2 and Dronninglund 154 K^2 [24]. However, it should be noted that when comparing these values, the operation of the PTES also needs to be taken into account. For example, the PTES in Marstal was only used for seasonal heat storage, where extended storage durations allowed heat diffusion to gradually degrade the temperature stratification. Nevertheless, the PTES in Dronninglund

served both as seasonal and short-term heat storage, making its degree of stratification comparable to that of the PTES in Høje Taastrup. These values indicate that the PTES in Høje Taastrup had a comparable degree of stratification with the PTES in Dronninglund, as their mean values are almost identical. The difference in the maximum values occurs because the PTES in Dronninglund had a temperature operation range from $8\text{--}90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which increases the values of the Stratification coefficient without necessarily indicating a higher degree of stratification.

The normalized exergy destruction has been shown to be a more representative method for evaluating stratification since it can compare storages with different heat losses without having biased results [24]. A higher degree of stratification corresponds to lower exergy destruction in a storage and, thus, a higher exergy efficiency as the exergy efficiency quantifies the amount of exergy lost due to mixing and heat losses. For 2024, the PTES in Høje Taastrup had exergy destruction of 33 MJ/m^3 . For comparison, the PTES in Dronninglund had 34 MJ/m^3 , and Marstal had 36 MJ/m^3 [24]. These results show that the performance of the Høje Taastrup PTES is comparable to Dronninglund. Based on this, there do not seem to be any negative effects on stratification when installing the diffusers at one end of the storage.

However, it should be noted that the PTES in Høje Taastrup has not yet operated at full charge/discharge thermal power for long periods. This can also be seen in Table 3, where the mean flow rate at the diffusers was between $200\text{--}330 \text{ m}^3/\text{hr}$, whereas the flow rate at full power is around $600 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. Thus, although the storage currently appears to have an acceptable degree of stratification, this should also be verified when operating at higher flow rates.

4.4. Efficiency

The storage efficiency was investigated in terms of energy and exergy. Table 4 presents the charged and discharged energy, internal energy change, heat loss, as well as the energy and exergy efficiency for each year. The overall energy efficiency for 2023 and 2024 was 89%, while the exergy efficiency was 75%. As expected, the exergy efficiency was lower than the energy efficiency as exergy also accounts for mixing in addition to heat losses.

It should be noted that the efficiency of the PTES is expected to increase in the future. First, the storage operation results in an increase in the average ground temperature, which will reduce the heat losses toward the ground. Literature has shown that the heat losses toward the ground in a short-term PTES stabilize approximately after 8 years of operation [27]. Second, additional storage cycles are expected to occur due to the expansion of the distribution grid and the longer operation forecasting horizon. All these factors will positively affect the storage efficiency, and the energy efficiency is expected to reach close to 95%.

For comparison, the PTES in Marstal had a mean energy efficiency of 63% and exergy of 48% from 2014–2017. Additionally, the PTES in Dronninglund had a mean energy efficiency of 92% and exergy of 73% from 2015–2019 [24]. It should be noted that, in general, due to the higher storage temperatures, short-term PTES have higher heat losses compared to seasonal ones. However, due to the higher number of storage cycles, short-term PTES are expected to have higher efficiencies as the heat loss is relatively lower per cycle.

5. Conclusions

The pit thermal energy storage (PTES) in Høje Taastrup, Denmark, is the first large-scale PTES to be operated as a short-term storage. This paper presented the system, several developments to the state-of-the-art, as well as an analysis of its performance. The main conclusions from this study were:

- PTES systems can successfully be used for short-term operation, provided they use a liner material that can withstand exposure to temperatures up to at least $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (for example, polypropylene with additives).

Fig. 8. Temperature profiles in the storage for January–March 2024.

Table 4

Yearly charged, discharged energy, internal energy change, heat loss, energy, and exergy efficiency. The measurements started in February 2023. The lid heat loss measurements started in August 2023.

Period	$E_{charged}$ [MWh]	$E_{discharged}$ [MWh]	$\Delta E_{internal}$ [MWh]	$E_{loss,total}$ [MWh]	$E_{loss,lid}$ [MWh]	η_E [%]	η_X [%]
2023	27,162	23,687	25	3450	472	88	76
2024	34,044	29,917	529	3598	1124	89	75
Total	61,206	53,604	644	7048	1597	89	75

- After two years of operation, the PTES in Høje Taastrup generally operates as expected, with the only deviation being a reduced heat load during the summer and autumn due to limitations in discharging to the district heating network.
- Compared to the PTES in Dronninglund, the PTES in Høje Taastrup had a slightly lower energy efficiency and higher exergy efficiency. However, since the ground heat losses have not yet stabilized and there are currently limitations in the local distribution grid, these values are expected to increase further.
- Similar stratification was achieved for the PTES in Høje Taastrup compared with existing systems, proving that using single-plate diffusers and placing them at the edge of the storage does not result in poor stratification, provided that the diffusers are properly dimensioned.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ioannis Sifnaios: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Adam R. Jensen:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The authors have shared a link to the data <https://github.com/PitStorages/HojeTaastrupData>.

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